

THE APPLICATION OF JEAN PIAGET'S THEORY TO E-LEARNING

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Abstract: E-Education has captured an important, sometimes the dominant role in the system of education all over the world during last decades. It has its pros and cons for lecturers and students. The author investigates some problems connected with the contemporary system of e- education , and the application of the constructivist approach in the modern system of e-education.

Key words: adult, constructivism, e-education, instructor, knowledge, personality, sense, student

Introduction

“ We cannot ever achieve final answers; rather we find new questions, we discover other possibilities which we might try out. Knowledge is ultimately governed by constructive alternativeness; everything can always be reconstructed.”

Salmon (2012)

The constructivist approach to higher education became the most popular one at European universities and higher schools during last decades. Constructivism, in contrast to behaviorism, has the origins of cognitive psychology concerned with the way by which the human mind thinks and learns, how people become involved in the process of learning in general, and in the process of e- education in particular nowadays. A student is seen as an active participant in the educational process according to a cognitive approach.

The author of the present research reveals and evaluates the current status of the constructivist approach to e- education and its usefulness for it.

The Problem of the constructivist approach to e - education was not investigated in Latvia, but it is very urgent nowadays, because the contemporary situation connected with the Covid-19 virus shows that everybody is influenced by the necessity to acquire new knowledge and skills with the help of new communication technologies, especially, when the European system of higher education uses e-learning and e-teaching everyday now.

There are many approaches, ways in which human thought was explored, and these ways varied considerably.

At one extreme, especially in the system of Distance Education, there are information theorists drawn the analogy of the human brain as a highly complex computer, they seek to explain its performance in terms of rules and models of learning. Different examples of this approach one can see in artificial intelligence systems' work, particularly, in varied models of memory and different cognitive processes.

At another extreme, it is the constructivist approach growing mainly on the base of the research by a Swiss developmental psychologist, Jean Piaget, also encompassing George Kelly's personal construct psychology, mainly concerned with the ways by which individuals come to make their own sense of the world.

The Aim of the proposed paper is to investigate the constructivist approach to e- education. The Object of the research is the constructivist approach to e-education.

The Method of the research is the scientific analysis of the methodological, psychological and pedagogical literature, connected with the given problem.

According to Burge & Roberts (2012), the constructivist approach to e-education is a process of creating meaning in which learners are actively engaged in the analysis of their own perspectives by obtaining new information and developing their own interpretations of it, where learners interact with each other and with the actual complex real-world online environments to construct a personal knowledge framework.

Let's analyze points of view of different scientists to the notion of constructivism that go beyond the interpersonal one.

“They direct attention to the ways in which activity is structured differently across contexts. If the cognitive development proceeds through the construction of meaning from activities, understanding the cultural structure of activities is crucial to understanding the ways in which meanings evolve differently in different contexts. Interpersonal interactions cannot provide insight into the sources of variation in developmental pathways unless they are embedded themselves in a cultural level of analysis that addresses the specific cross-contextual differences in terms of which interpersonal relations vary” Bidel (2014).

But Slavin (2016), believes that constructivism is a view of the cognitive development as a process in which students build systems of the meaning and understanding of reality through their experiences and interactions, actively construct knowledge by continually assimilating and accommodating new information.

The author shares points of view of Brooks & Brooks (2013), and Cranton (2004), that constructivism is the process where learners actively create knowledge and meaning through the experimentation, exploration, manipulation and testing of ideas in reality, where collaboration, shared goals, teamwork, group activities, simulations, the use of open-ended questions are powerful forces in the learning process. An instructor acts as a facilitator of the e-educational process. This is the essence of e-self-directed learning, as it empowers students to follow those interactions wherever they may lead and are not dependent on the instructor.

Jonassen (2015), believes that the facilitation of the online learning environments that foster personal meaning-making, as well as the social construction of knowledge and meaning through interactions with communities of students is preferred to the instructor's interventions controlled the sequence and content of e-instructions.

To the author's mind, the process of e-education is learner-centered, taking the lead and determining the flow and direction of the process.

Let's reconsider the definitional elements of e- education:

- the separation of an instructor and a learner in time and place for a majority of the instructional processes;
- the connection through educational media;
- a volitional control of the learning process resting with a learner.

It becomes clear that the more active learning models are the more models of choice for the online learning environment could be. By given limitations of the access to students, the time and distance, the instructor can't control successfully how or what is being learned. And because students are left to their own devices, it is up to learners to make sense of the core of knowledge associated with a learning course being delivered by themselves.

The instructor supports this e-process through the usage of collaborative assignments, the facilitation of active discussions, the promotion of the development in critical thinking and research skills. The outcome is the online learning environment's enrichment in the potential for collaborative learning and social construction of meaning.

The author would like to analyze a constructivist approach to the development of the Bronfenbrenner's (2017) Ecological Systems Theory, which views a student as a person developed within a complex system of relationships. According to this theory, learner relationships are affected by multiple levels of the environment from the intimate levels of parent-child interaction-the microsystem-to the immediate settings of a family, school, and neighbourhood-the mesosystem- to the broad contexts of society and culture-the eco-system.

An important implication of the ecological system theory to the process of e- education is that changes at any level have an impact on the development, which supports the idea that the prevention and intervention programs or services can have the significant impact on students' well-being and education.

The constructivist approach to learning means, to the author's mind, that students will be gathering information and analyzing it as they jointly explore topics and test theoretical ideas against the real-life situations and their own practical knowledge. So rather than students' listening to the lecturer's constructions of knowledge, they play an active role in being their own "knowledge architect". This type of learning is rooted in the meaning-making process that is central to constructivism, which we have already established as a major feature of the online lecture-room. The predisposition of people for constructing their own meanings is recognized as the key for designed effective learning in all settings, including workplace settings.

According to the constructivist approach, students:

- ❖ analyze concepts, theories, principles;
 - ❖ apply them to the real world problems;
 - ❖ reflect on their own experiences of learning;
 - ❖ assess the relevance of theories and practical experience to own life contexts;
 - ❖ contribute constructively to all kinds of discussions;
 - ❖ support and challenge group members in their explorations, and
 - ❖ carry out self-assessment of their learning
- Piaget (1950).

The author shares the point of view of educational researchers Haynes, Davis, McKibbon and Tugwel (2014) that e-education is a constructive process in which the learner interacts with new information in order to establish personally relevant meaning of this information. As the topic is e - education, the interaction with new online information is the essential ingredient in this process. The challenge for instructional designers is to organize learning opportunities to support such an interaction.

Let's analyze the constructivist approach in connection with e-education more in detail.

Jean Piaget is considered to be a father of the Theory of Constructivism. Jean Piaget is the most dominant figure in the constructivist movement because he is the first researcher stressed the main emphasis on the constructivist nature of the learning process.

The main idea of Piaget (1950) is based on the idea that knowledge is constructed by a learner in mental activities. In contrast to the more traditional views seen learning as simply the accumulation of facts or the development of skills, the main underlying assumption of constructivism is that individuals are actively involved right from their birth in constructing the personal meaning that is their own personal understanding from their experiences.

A student is brought into the central focus of the educational process, he/she is an active participant seeking meaning. Each of them generates own rules and mental models used to use sense of their experience more successfully.

Piaget is more interested in the ways in which people come to know things as they developed from infancy to adulthood. Thus, his theory is one which is action-based. The constructivist approach by Piaget is more concerned with the process of learning than what is learned. It suggests that we come to know things as a direct result of our personal experiences, but we make sense of those experiences at different stages of our lives.

Piaget's theory is based on learners passing through a series of stages. For an infant, the most important way of exploring the environment is through his basic senses. It is the sensory-motor stage of learning. The next stage is the intuitive, pre-operational stage, it is between two and seven. The concrete operational stage is at the age of seven of a child, this stage depends on concrete examples. Finally, there is a move to formal operational thinking when abstract reasoning becomes increasingly possible. It happens, for Piaget, during adolescent and adult years.

There are three basic components of Piaget's Constructivist Theory (1950):

- schemas (building blocks of knowledge);
- adaptation processes enabled the transition from one stage to another one (equilibrium, assimilation, and accommodation);
- stages of cognitive development.

Jean Piaget (1950) viewed the intellectual development as a process of adaptation (adjustment) to the world. The author supports the point of view of Piaget (1950) who defines the human cognitive development as mainly a process of maturation, within which genetics and experience interact. The developing mind is viewed as constantly seeking equilibration, i.e. a balance between what is known and what was currently being experienced. This is accomplished by the complementary processes of assimilation and accommodation.

Assimilation is the process by which incoming information is changed in our minds so that we can fit it in with what we already know. Accommodation is the process by which we modify what we have already known to obtain new information. Working together, these two processes contribute to what Piaget terms the central process of the cognitive adaptation.

This is the essential aspect of e-education. Instructors should encourage students to pay attention to the process of learning rather than the end product of it, to use active methods of “reconstructing the truth”. The author would like to draw the reader’s attention to some central aspects which are of particular significance for computer-mediated e-education.

- First, everybody can see the importance of a learner to be an individual, actively involved in constructing the meaning. When students learn any subject, they are actively involved in making their own sense of this subject as well as of tasks proposed to them.

- Second, the development of thinking and its relationship to a subject and experience become a central focus of e-education.

- Third, a care should be taken to match requirements of any e-task to the cognitive level of a student. These tasks set by an instructor from the electronic lecture-room should be neither too abstract for those who are not yet conceptually capable of functioning at this level, nor too simple for the level of the student’s competence.

- Fourth, one can see the application of Piaget’s notions of assimilation and accommodation to learning a new subject. When students receive a new input of the subject, they need to modify what they already know about this subject (accommodation) to “fit” the new information in their existing knowledge (assimilation). In this way students’ knowledge of how the system of the new subject operates gradually develops.

The next famous follower of the constructivist movement, whose Theory of Personal Constructs (1955) has profound implications for lecturers and educational psychologists, is George Kelly. Kelly (1955) believes that people as scientists constantly seek to make the sense of their world, they carry out their own personal experiments, construct hypotheses, theories and actively seek to confirm or disconfirm them.

The pattern of a man’s construction is called a construct, in other words, a construct is the meaning we give to our surrounding reality. Each person sets up his/her own network of pathways leading to the future. In order to understand someone, one should understand his/her personal construct system (Kelly, 1955).

These personal theories or “constructs” people place over their impressions of any new events or people with whom they get in touch in order to establish some kind of reasonable “fit”. For Kelly, learning involves students to make their own sense of new information, and this is especially important for e-education. Students are actively involved in constructing their own personal understanding of things, and this understanding will be different for different people. Kelly(1955) argues that differences in human behaviour largely result from differences in the ways people perceive and construct the world.

This statement completely coincides with the point of view of one of the creators of the Learning Styles’ Theory - Rita Dunn (1989), who believes that people concentrate on, absorb, process and retain new information differently according to 23 elements of instructional environment;

- ❖ immediate environment (noise, temperature, light, design),
- ❖ emotionality,
- ❖ sociological preference (learning alone; with peers; with adults present),
- ❖ physical characteristics (auditory, visual, tactile/kinesthetic preference, time of day...),

❖ psychological inclinations (global/analytic, hemispheric preferences, impulsive/reflective).

All these elements define learning style of students. Keefe (1987), gives one of the classic definitions of learning styles: “ Learning styles are the cognitive, affective, and physiological traits that serve as relatively stable indicators of how learners perceive, interact with, and respond to the learning environment”. Kolb (1987), believes that there are four main styles of learning, which are represented by the Diverger, Assimilator, Converger, and Accommodator.

All these definitions are closely connected with the main postulates of the constructivist movement:

- knowledge is constructed not transmitted;
- prior knowledge impacts the learning process;
- building useful knowledge requires effortful and purposeful activities.
- knowledge is constructed by a learner, not passively received from the environment.

Kelly(1955) believes that students are active participants in deciding how to act and they made such decisions on the basis of what was made the sense to them personally. Each person’s individual construction of the world depends upon their previous experiences, which also influence how they anticipate what will happen in the future.

Instructors should see the differences related to each style. For example, the Accommodator will be comfortably involved in a task completion and taking the real-world risks and be impatient with too many theoretical talks; the Assimilator, on the other hand, will be happy linking a wide variety of ideas in order to build models or theories. Working together, these two persons may make a great team – once they accept their different ways of getting and processing information.

The author would like to set out some important implication of taking a personal construct approach to e-education.

- First, we can make a clear distinction between meaningful and meaningless learning activities in e-education. E - learning does not entail the reception of ready-made facts, but must involve building of new personal meanings and understanding. Only by developing their own understanding of the world it is possible for students to be changed and developed.

The author supports the point of view of Kelly who believes that a meaningful activity is one that encourages the process of making sense, of fitting or mapping the new onto the old to create new understanding.

- Second, as Salmon (2012) points out, though each of individuals inhabits the unique experiential world, if it is to be a social world, we must find ways of reaching common understanding together with others. The human enterprise depends on a shared online reality. Instructors and learners should be as much as possible involved in e-education and try to achieve some kind of shared understanding of what is happening in their electronic space.

- Third, instructors should realize that although a curriculum may be set down precisely for them, it inevitably becomes shaped by them into something personal which reflects their own belief systems, their thoughts and feelings about both the content of their lectures and learners, views of the world in general.

The usage of the constructivist approach does not imply that learning standards go downhill, or that the instructor becomes unnecessary. Students work hard to analyze the complexities of the real world contexts, to figure out solutions to messy problems or apply new skills.

Instructors guide and challenge rather than serve only a transmission function.

The author shares the point of view of Burge and Roberts (2012:20), who believe that there are the following implications of applying the constructivist approach to e-education:

1. Learning resources should have some or all of these characteristics:
 - relevance to a learner and to the real-world problems and contexts;

- a variety of problems and contexts (avoiding fear of information);
 - controversial or complex problems (depth of information);
 - conflicting ideas and attitudes in a context;
 - personal practical knowledge held by a learner.
2. The constructive student in the electronic space:
- challenges her/his own knowledge and values;
 - uses many types of thinking, such as metaphorical, intuitive, creative and logical/analytical;
 - discovers and analyzes all elements in a complex situation;
 - generates alternative solutions or procedures;
 - checks a proposed new solution or procedure;
 - uses errors as a part of learning;
 - thinks in order to speak;
 - revisits new learning to develop ideas in more depth across new situations;
 - accepts the ambiguities in how the real world operates.
3. The constructive instructor in the electronic lecture-room:
- encourages students to produce, not reproduce, ideas;
 - helps learners to revisit information for the greater depth of analysis;
 - lets learners to struggle a bit to figure things out;
 - offers learners the opportunity to watch an expert in action;
 - asks for proof of learning, for example: "How did you reach that conclusion?"(a new idea), or "Show how you do that" (a new skill);
 - confirms, corrects and challenges students;
 - helps students to use different perspectives to look at a problem;
 - knows when to get out of the students' space;
 - ensures access to adequate resources.

The author would like to add that confusion is an expected factor in all kinds of learning, especially when students try to organize mass of incoming information in a hurry.

Instructors need to resist own desire to rescue students from their confusion, as they need to work through their confusion to develop better learning skills.

A careful instructor, to the author's mind, will assess whether learners can be left alone for a while to handle the confusion and decide when the assistance should be offered, first by group peers, and then by the instructor. These choices demand good judgment that is based on the instructor's knowledge of students.

Conclusion

The author can conclude that the constructivist approach to e-education identifies four key sets of factors influenced the learning process on the Information Highway:

- instructors,
- learners,
- tasks, and
- contexts.

None of these factors exists in isolation. They all interact as a part of a dynamic process.

All instructors in the electronic lecture - room selected tasks according to their beliefs about e-teaching and learning, should take into account approaches to learning of their students and their cognitive level.

Learners interpret tasks in the ways that are meaningful and personal to them as individuals. A task, to the author's mind, is therefore an interface between the instructor and learners.

These three elements: the instructor, the task, and the learner are in this way a dynamic equilibrium. The context in which e-learning takes place plays an important part in shaping what happens within it. That includes the emotional environment, the physical environment; the whole educational ethos; the wider social environment; the political environment and the cultural setting.

That can be represented as a set of concentric circles, influencing each other, with the participants, playing the important role in shaping these environments. The keys to the creation of a learning community and successful facilitation online are simple. They are, to the author's mind, the following:

- honesty,
- responsiveness,
- relevance,
- respect,
- professionalism,
- openness, and
- empowerment.

Stressing the importance of the e-learning community as a central feature, the role and importance of each of these keys to success will become clear. Group members should feel safe in expressing themselves without fear of how they will be perceived, allowing for active, rich discussions. The implications are that as educators, we should be able to create atmosphere of safety and community in all of our learning settings, whether they are electronic or face to face.

Instructors need to act as gentle guides while participants are developing norms and rules as they go. Facilitators, participants should become equal partners in the development of a successful online learning community. The development of community as a part of the learning process helps to create rich and powerful learning experiences.

E-education is concerned not just with theories of instruction, but with learning to learn, developing knowledge, skills and strategies to continue to learn and adapt, with making learning experiences meaningful and relevant to the individual, with the development and growth as a whole unique person. In order to do that well, we must understand mental models that students use to perceive the world and assumptions they make to support those models.

Instructors should use the constructivist approach to teaching by their strong support of discovery approaches which requires a student to construct information and knowledge by discovering the relationships existed among concepts and principles, change their world by active mental work.

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